

1 **Direct membrane filtration of municipal wastewater assisted by natural tannin-based**
2 **coagulant: Insights into membrane fouling and methane production**

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12 **Highlight**

- 13 - Tannin-based coagulants effectively reduce fouling in DMF systems.
14 - Significant reduction of external fouling with the application of tannin.
15 - Tannin reduced biopolymer deposition, enhancing membrane performance.
16 - Early-stage methane production improved, supporting energy recovery.
17 - Tannin is a suitable solution for DMF of wastewater.

18

19 **Abstract**

20 This study evaluates the use of tannin-based coagulants in direct membrane filtration (DMF)
21 systems for the up-concentration of organic matter in municipal wastewater and its effects on
22 membrane fouling and methane production by anaerobic digestion. Tannin, a natural and
23 biodegradable coagulant, was applied at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, and 50 mg L⁻¹. The
24 fouling behavior was hydraulic assessed by a series of filtration tests under constant flux, while
25 external and internal foulants were widely characterized, including liquid chromatography
26 coupled with a dissolved organic carbon analyzer. The results revealed a significant reduction
27 in total fouling resistance, particularly external fouling associated with the formation of a cake
28 layer. At concentration of 30 mg L⁻¹, tannin effectively reduced external fouling by promoting
29 particle aggregation and reducing biopolymer deposition, particularly proteins, which were
30 reduced by up to 80%. That coagulant concentration significantly reduces internal foulants, as
31 evidenced by the sharp decline in biopolymer concentration (from 5.6 to 1.3 g m⁻²) and the
32 substantial reduction in humic substances (from 11.2 to 3.2 g m⁻²). Moreover, the anaerobic
33 digestion by BMP tests demonstrated that tannin addition enhanced early-stage methane
34 production due to the presence of easily biodegradable organic matter, leading a methane yield
35 of 391 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ VS. In conclusion, tannin-based coagulant presents a promising solution for
36 improving DMF performance by reducing fouling and enhancing energy recovery through
37 biogas production.

38 **Keywords:** resource recovery, water reuse, membrane, biogas, coagulants, anaerobic
39 digestion.

40 1. Introduction

41 Over the last decade, pre-concentration of organic matter emerged as an innovative layout
42 to boost energy recovery toward self-energy and carbon neutral wastewater treatment. In this
43 new configuration, the organic content of raw wastewater (i.e., chemical energy) is
44 concentrated as much as possible for further anaerobic degradation and biogas recovery,
45 avoiding the loss of potential energy by biological aerobic oxidation as conventionally
46 performed [1]. Among the current approaches, direct membrane filtration (DMF) offers great
47 potential for redirecting the organic matter from wastewater [2,3]. The approach refers to the
48 use of a membrane process for wastewater filtration after preliminary and/or primary treatment,
49 which can be integrated into existing treatment systems, providing flexibility in design and
50 capacity [4–6]. Additionally, due to the high efficiency of microfiltration (MF) and
51 ultrafiltration (UF) membranes in removing particulate material, colloidal particles, and
52 pathogenic organisms through the size exclusion mechanism, a high clarified permeate with
53 low organic matter content and rich in nutrients is produced for fertigation or landscaping reuse
54 [7,8].

55 Although the DMF enables the production of a reusable permeate and the redirection of
56 up to 80% of the organic matter found in the wastewater [9], the sustainable and economic
57 viability of the system depends on effective fouling control, which remains a challenge in this
58 configuration [10]. Given the high amount of organic matter of different composition and size,
59 as well as particulate material in municipal wastewater (MWW), a significant physical-
60 chemical interaction between foulants and membrane is expected, leading to a severe fouling
61 in a short term [11,12]. Biopolymer clusters, such as humic-like, polysaccharides- and protein-
62 like substances, were the predominant foulants in MWW, being proteins responsible for more
63 severe fouling than humic substances [12]. Furthermore, by extending the filtration period of
64 MWW, increased pore clogging and cake layer compression led to more severe irreversible

65 fouling, which required daily chemical cleaning and demanded more energy for the filtration,
66 thereby increasing operational costs [10]. On the other hand, effective control of fouling can
67 not only reduce the need for chemical cleaning, but also result in a self-energy system [13].
68 Net energy production ranging from 0.029 to 0.25 kWh m⁻³ through the anaerobic digestion of
69 the concentrate has been demonstrated when effective fouling mitigation strategies are applied
70 [3,5,13–15]. This highlights the significant impact that proper fouling control can have on
71 enhancing energy efficiency in the DMF system.

72 Coagulants have been used in direct membrane filtration as a strategy for maintaining
73 higher permeate fluxes and acceptable fouling rates in the application of MF and UF within
74 this innovative resource recovery wastewater treatment approach. Metal-based coagulants such
75 as polyaluminum chloride (PACl) is the most widely used in concentration range from 20 – 60
76 mg L⁻¹, either alone or in combination with adsorbents and physical methods [11,15–17].
77 Generally, these coagulants work by destabilizing particles, enabling their aggregation and
78 promoting the reduction of colloidal and organic compounds that can act as membrane foulants
79 [18–20]. The reduction of small particles that could directly block membrane pores, combined
80 with the decrease of the pollutant load, is therefore the main reason for the reduction of fouling
81 in DMF systems. For instance, Zhao et al. [11] observed that PACl-assisted flat-sheet ceramic
82 membrane filtration of wastewater allowed maintaining a stable flux of 41 (L m⁻² h⁻¹ – LMH),
83 requiring chemical cleaning every 3 – 5 d by a chemical backwash for only 10 min.
84 Additionally, coagulants offer high flexibility to be integrated with membranes to reduce
85 fouling, including configurations as in-line pre-coagulation, coagulation and flocculation
86 (C/F), and coagulation, flocculation, and sedimentation (CF-S).

87 However, despite promising results in fouling mitigation with metal-based coagulants, their
88 use has increasingly been questioned due to negative impacts on the environment and human
89 health, as well as on the anaerobic digestion process [18,21]. By dosing PACl at 24 mg_{Al} L⁻¹

90 in raw wastewater, Lin et al. [22] found a 47% reduction in the specific hydrolysis rate constant
91 ($K_{h,p}$) for sludge fermentation compared to non-coagulated sludge. Likewise, a drastic
92 reduction in biogas production from 0.40 to 0.10 m³ kg⁻¹ COD was observed with increasing
93 doses of FeCl₃ and Al₂(SO₄)₃, supposedly caused by inhibitory effects of anaerobic
94 microorganisms and the reduced availability of phosphate and trace elements adsorbed on the
95 precipitated metal hydroxides [23].

96 Although low doses, metal coagulants have limited or no effect on anaerobic digestion [24],
97 the digestate could contain high levels of these metal, potentially leading to secondary pollution
98 concerns [25,26]. Jin et al. [27] reported aluminum levels of 369 mg g⁻¹ SS in the concentrate
99 of a UF membrane system for pre-concentration of organic matter from wastewater with 30
100 mg L⁻¹ of PACl. Therefore, research on the application of novel eco-friendly and recyclable
101 coagulants is an important step to control fouling and, at the same time, to avoid some
102 drawbacks of metallic coagulants.

103 Natural-based organic coagulants represent an attractive approach to replace widely used
104 synthetic metallic coagulants in DMF. Some natural-based coagulants (e.g., chitosan, Moringa
105 oleifera extracts, tannin) are less harmful or even non-harmful [18,28]. They generate
106 biodegradable sludge in smaller amounts, potentially reducing disposal costs, which can be
107 easily obtained from renewable feedstocks and being less affected by water pH [29], making
108 them potentially sustainable for organic matter concentration and subsequent anaerobic
109 valorization. Tannin-based coagulants have emerged as a viable option due to their natural
110 plant origin, biodegradability, and effectiveness in aggregating suspended solids and colloidal
111 particles [26]. Incorporating tannin-based coagulants into the DMF systems could potentially
112 enhance performance by reducing membrane fouling, without affecting anaerobic digestion or
113 causing coagulant accumulation in the digestate.

114 The use of tannin-based coagulants has increased in recent years, including applications for
115 water treatment [30], post-treatment of UASB reactor effluents [31], industrial effluents [32],
116 landfill leachates [33], and assisting in the separation of microalgal biomass [34]. To date,
117 existing research on tannin and porous membrane is limited and inconclusive, and their
118 effectiveness in preventing fouling in different matrices is still unclear. For instance, Ragio et
119 al. [35] observed higher performance with tannin than with PACl when investigating the use
120 of coagulant to reduce fouling during de UF of a UASB reactor effluent. This improvement
121 was attributed to the formation of strong flocs larger than 200 μm which facilitated removal by
122 crossflow filtration. On the other hand, Gonçalves et al. [36] reported minimal improvement
123 with the use of a tannin-based coagulant for the ultrafiltration (UF) of a microalgae suspension
124 from a high-rate phototrophic pond. Therefore, understanding the interplay between the matrix
125 composition and the natural tannin-based coagulant efficacy is necessary for optimizing the
126 ultrafiltration process in DMF applications.

127 From holistic perspective, this study investigated the influence of tannin-based coagulants
128 in the upstream concentration processes of organic substances during DMF of municipal
129 wastewater. By facilitating particle aggregation, tannin-based coagulants are expected to
130 modify the characteristics of the fouling layer, potentially making it less dense and easier to
131 manage. Understanding these interactions is an important step for optimizing the DMF process
132 and enhancing its efficiency. Moreover, the study assesses the impact of organic up-
133 concentration with tannin coagulant on methane production during anaerobic digestion. The
134 key objectives of this research include: 1) evaluating the effect of different concentration of
135 tannin-based coagulants in reducing membrane fouling in UF processes of coagulated-
136 flocculated wastewater, 2) studying the characteristics of the fouling layer formed with and
137 without the coagulant, 3) assessing the impact of organic up-concentration on methane
138 production in anaerobic digestion.

139 2. Materials and Methods

140 2.1. Wastewater samples and experimental set-up

141 The wastewater was collected at the Wastewater Treatment Plant of the Autonomous
142 University of Madrid (WWTP-UAM) after preliminary treatment, which included mechanical
143 screening with a step screen and a rectangular constant-velocity grit chamber (Figure 1). Before
144 being used in the filtration tests, the collected samples were passed through a 1.0 mm mesh
145 sieve. After collection and initial characterization (Table 1), the samples were stored at 4 °C
146 until used in the experiments.

147 **Table 1:** Main characteristics of wastewater from preliminary treatment.

Parameter	Min – Max
pH	7.2 – 7.9
Total COD (mg L ⁻¹)	223 – 343
Soluble COD (mg L ⁻¹)	112 – 168
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)	53.6 – 93.4
Total nitrogen (mg N L ⁻¹)	38.6 – 59.2
Ammonia nitrogen (mg N L ⁻¹)	30.1 – 57.6
Total phosphorous (mg P L ⁻¹)	6.3 – 9.8
Turbidity (NTU)	118 – 219
Apparent color (uC)	1292 – 1476
True color (uC)	87 – 177

148
149 The membrane filtration system consisted of a sample tank reservoir connected to a
150 peristaltic pump (Masterflex L/S), which fed and recirculated the wastewater through the
151 membrane compartment (Fig. 1). During the tests, an upward velocity of 0.43 cm s⁻¹ was
152 maintained, corresponding to a shear rate of approximately 1000 s⁻¹. The permeate was
153 suctioned by a peristaltic pump (Masterflex L/S) into a tank placed on a digital balance, and
154 the membrane flux was calculated based on the weight of the permeate. A pressure transmitter

155 connected to a data logger was used to record pressure data during the tests, which was utilized
156 to calculate the transmembrane pressure (TMP).

157 A vertically mounted submerged hollow-fiber ultrafiltration membrane module (HF-
158 UF) was used for the filtration assessments (Figure 1). Each module had 245 cm² of effective
159 membrane area, distributed across 10 PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) hollow fibers, each 30
160 cm long, with a nominal pore size of 0.03 μm (PURON® Hollow Fiber - Koch Membranes).
161 Pressure Decay Test (PDT), as described by Guo et al. [37] were used to evaluate the integrity
162 of the five producer modules, resulting in less than 0.12 psi min⁻¹ for all modules. In addition
163 to PDT, the membrane modules were also characterized based on their permeability for
164 deionized (DI) water, which ranged from 709 to 757 L m⁻² h⁻¹ bar⁻¹.

165
166 **Figure 1.** Wastewater sample preparation and schematic diagram of HF-UF crossflow
167 filtration.

168 The assisted filtration of wastewater with the tannin-based coagulant was performed
169 using the commercial product Tanfloc, modified by a Mannich reaction as described in
170 TANAC S.A. patent [38]. The tannin-based coagulant manufactured by TANAC is a natural
171 cationic coagulant produced from the bark of *Acacia mearnsii*. It has a charge density of 0.67
172 mEq g⁻¹ (pH = 7) [39] is effective over a pH range of 4.5 – 8 and has no significant effects on

173 the pH [35]. A tannin stock solution with a concentration of 10.0 g L⁻¹ was prepared using
174 deionized water for the experiments. The stock solutions were applied directly throughout the
175 experimental process without additional dilution.

176 Based on previous studies using this coagulant in UASB reactor effluents [31] and jar
177 tests with wastewater from the WWTP-UAM, the filtration experiments for organic matter
178 concentration assisted by tannin were carried out with dosages of 10, 20, 30, and 50 mg L⁻¹.
179 Given that coagulation and flocculation generally lead to a greater reduction in total and
180 hydraulically irreversible fouling compared to coagulation alone [40], the sample preparation
181 in jar test included adding the coagulant to the raw wastewater under rapid mixing conditions
182 ($G = 350 \text{ s}^{-1}$, HRT = 1 min) followed by flocculation ($G = 20 \text{ s}^{-1}$, HRT = 15 min). The
183 coagulated and flocculated sample for each coagulant dosage (i.e., TAN-10, TAN-20, TAN-
184 30, and TAN-50 mg L⁻¹) was then used in the filtration tests for organic matter concentration
185 and fouling assessment.

186 **2.2. Fouling assessment**

187 The filtration experiments were conducted in two stages to analyze the hydraulic
188 performance and fouling propensity with different coagulant dosages (Figure 2). In the first
189 stage, the tannin-coagulated and flocculated wastewater samples (TAN-10, TAN-20, TAN-30,
190 and TAN-50) and the control (raw wastewater – RWW) were concentrated under a constant
191 flux condition ($\approx 40 \text{ LMH}$) until a concentration factor of 5 was reached (Figure 2). At this
192 stage, the increase in transmembrane pressure (TMP) was simultaneously monitored and used
193 as an indicator of fouling. At the end, cleaning with deionized water and sodium hydroxide
194 solution (0.02%) were performed to estimate the hydraulic resistances associated with each
195 fouling fraction.

196 The concentrated samples produced in the first stage were then used to evaluate the
197 effect of tannin on the threshold flux (J_{Th}), defined as the highest flux at which $dTMP/dt$

198 remained below 3.0×10^{-4} bar s^{-1} , with fouling rates below this value considered low [41]. The
199 determination of the threshold flux relied on progressively increasing flux steps during total
200 recycle mode, where both retentate and permeate were systematically returned to the feed tank,
201 and TMP was simultaneously monitored to identify significant changes. Before each filtration
202 flux increment, a 30-second backwash was performed. Based on the experimental results, the
203 increase in the fouling rate was evaluated by determining the values of $dTMP/dt$ for each
204 constant flux step, representing the TMP increase during the last 5 min of each flux step.

205 Finally, the reproducibility of the filtration tests was validated by conducting a long-
206 term test (20 h) with the coagulant concentration considered most effective in the concentration
207 stage compared to a control sample of wastewater. For this test, a new wastewater sample was
208 collected from the WWTP-UAM, and the filtrations were carried out under constant flux
209 conditions based on the values estimated in the threshold flux tests (i.e., 20 LMH). At the end
210 of the filtration, another cleaning was performed to estimate the resistances associated with
211 fouling.

212 The hydraulic quantification of fouling was conducted using the series resistance
213 model, based on Darcy's Law. During constant flux filtration, the rise in TMP is directly linked
214 to an increase in resistance, as shown in Equation 1.

$$215 \quad R_t = \frac{\Delta P_t}{\eta J_s} = R_m + R_f \quad (1)$$

216 Where R_t represents the total resistance, including the intrinsic resistance of the membrane (R_m
217) and the total fouling resistance R_f , ΔP_t denotes the transmembrane pressure, J_s is the flux for
218 the sample and η refers to the viscosity.

219

220 **Figure 2.** Filtration experiments protocol to analyze hydraulic performance and fouling
 221 propensity, where VCF means volumetric concentration factor.

222 The total fouling resistance (Eq. 2) was further divided into external resistance (R_{ext}),
 223 defined in this study as the resistance removable through deionized water recirculation and
 224 calculated using Equation 3, as well as internal resistance R_{int} (Eq. 4), where the foulants could
 225 only be removed by chemical cleaning.

$$226 \quad R_f = R_{ext} + R_{int} \quad (2)$$

$$227 \quad R_{ext} = R_t - R_{rinsed} = R_t - \frac{\Delta P_t}{\eta J_{w1}} \quad (3)$$

$$228 \quad R_{int} = R_{rinsed} - R_{NaOH} = R_{rinsed} - \frac{\Delta P_t}{\eta J_{w2}} \quad (4)$$

229 The material extracted from the membrane using each cleaning method was collected
 230 and analyzed. For external fouling, the foulants were removed by recirculating 150 mL of
 231 deionized water for 20 min. The collected solution was analyzed for suspended solids, chemical
 232 oxygen demand (COD), proteins, and carbohydrates. Additionally, to provide valuable insights
 233 into how different components contribute to fouling and how they interact with the membrane
 234 surface and porous, the dissolved fraction of external fouling and the compounds related to
 235 internal fouling (extracted from the membrane using a 0.02% NaOH solution for 24 h [42])

236 were characterized and quantified using Liquid Chromatography coupled with a Carbon
237 Analyzer (LC-DOC).

238 To evaluate the contribution of tannin coagulant to internal fouling, a static adsorption
239 test was carried out using a 50 mg L⁻¹ tannin solution, as described by [43]. In summary, a
240 hollow-fiber membrane module was used to conduct the tests. Initially, filtration with
241 deionized water was performed to characterize the hydraulic properties of the membranes.
242 Subsequently, the membranes were soaked in a 50 mg L⁻¹ tannin solution for 24 h. After this
243 period, the membranes were removed, and a new filtration with DI water was performed to
244 determine the internal resistance of the membrane due to coagulant adsorption. Tannin solution
245 samples were taken before and after the tests to determine the DOC concentration and estimate
246 the maximum adsorption capacity at equilibrium, expressed by equation 5.

$$247 \quad q = \frac{(C_0 - C)V}{A} \quad (5)$$

248 where C₀ and C are the initial and equilibrium DOC concentrations, V is the solution volume,
249 and A is the membrane module area. Additionally, the 50 mg L⁻¹ tannin solution was also
250 characterized through LC-DOC.

251 **2.3. Batch anaerobic digestion tests**

252 The biochemical methane potential (BMP) test was used as a standard reference to
253 evaluate the effect of tannin-based coagulant on the anaerobic digestion of the concentrate from
254 DMF. The batch anaerobic digestion experiments were carried out in triplicate, using glass
255 serum vials with a total volume of 120 mL, as reported by Villamil et al. [44]. Each vial
256 contained a mixture of inoculum and substrate in a 2:1 ratio regarding volatile solids (VS)
257 concentration, along with a macro- and micronutrient solution prepared as described by
258 Angelidaki and Sanders [45], totaling a reaction volume of 60 mL. The vials were sealed with
259 rubber stoppers, purged with N₂ to ensure an oxygen-free atmosphere and kept stirring in a
260 water bath at 35 °C. Anaerobic granular sludge from an internal circulation reactor treating

261 beverage wastewater was used as inoculum, with the following characteristics: 45.4 ± 1.8 g TS
262 L^{-1} ; 36.1 ± 1.2 g VS L^{-1} ; pH 7.3. The substrates included samples from DMF concentrates
263 without coagulant (10.7 ± 0.49 g TS L^{-1} ; 10.1 ± 1.3 g VS L^{-1} ; pH 7.3) and coagulated and
264 flocculated with 50 mg L^{-1} tannin (9.3 ± 1.1 g TS L^{-1} ; 8.6 ± 0.8 g VS L^{-1} ; pH 7.3), as well as
265 aerobic sludge collected from the activated sludge reactor at the UAM wastewater treatment
266 plant (13.9 ± 0.6 g TS L^{-1} ; 10.6 ± 0.2 g VS L^{-1} ; pH 7.1). The BMP test was conducted with the
267 highest tannin concentration to evaluate a possible inhibitory effect on methane production.

268 The headspace pressure in the glass serum vials was monitored using a digital
269 manometer (ifm, PN 7097) [46] and used to estimate the biogas volume produced, which was
270 subsequently normalized to standard temperature and pressure conditions (273 K and 1 atm).
271 The methane volume was calculated based on the methane content in the biogas, determined
272 through a gas chromatograph with a thermal conductivity detector (GC-2014, Shimadzu) [47].
273 After each measurement, the pressure in the reactors was released, and the cumulative methane
274 production was determined by summing the daily production. Net methane production was
275 calculated by subtracting the methane yield measured in the blank control, thus accounting for
276 any production resulting from biomass decay and residual substrates. Finally, the methane yield
277 was expressed in mL STP g^{-1} VS, based on the initial characterization of the substrates used.

278 **2.4. Analytical methods**

279 The concentrations of COD, TS, VS and total suspended solids (TSS) were measured
280 following methods 5220 C, 2540 B, 2540 E and 2540 D from the Standard Methods [48]. The
281 open reflux method described by Raposo et al. [49] was employed for COD determination in
282 samples with high solids content. Total nitrogen, ammoniacal nitrogen, and total phosphorus
283 were quantified using Hach kits and analyzed with a spectrophotometer (model DR 3900 -
284 Hach). Proteins and carbohydrates were measured via spectrophotometry based on the methods
285 of Lowry [50] and [51], respectively. Turbidity and color were assessed using a turbidimeter

286 (model HI93703) and a multiparameter analyzer (model HI83308) from Hanna instruments,
287 respectively. The particle size distribution (PSD) was determined by laser diffraction using the
288 MASTERSIZER 2000 (Malvern) equipment, with a measurement range of particle sizes
289 between 20 nm and 2000 μm . Liquid chromatography coupled with a dissolved organic carbon
290 (DOC) analyzer (LC-DOC) from DOC-Labor (Germany) was used for the quantification of
291 total organic carbon and chromatographable organic carbon. The latter was fractionated by size
292 exclusion chromatography into biopolymers (high molecular weight $> 100,000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), humic
293 substances (HS), building blocks (i.e., subunits of HS with molecular weights of 300 – 450 g
294 mol^{-1}), low molecular weight (LMW) organic acids (i.e., aliphatic, low-molecular-weight
295 monoprotic acids that elute due to anionic repulsion), and LMW neutrals (i.e., weakly charged
296 or uncharged hydrophilic or slightly hydrophobic "amphiphilic" compounds appearing in this
297 fraction). The concentrations of LMW acids were mostly unquantifiable and, for this reason,
298 were not included in the results.

299 **3. Results and discussion**

300 **3.1. Effects of tannin concentration on the hydraulic performance of membranes**

301 Figure 3-a shows the variation in TMP during constant flux filtration of wastewater
302 (around 40 LMH) as a function of permeate recovery, using various concentrations of tannin-
303 based coagulant (TAN-10, TAN-20, TAN-30, TAN-50) and a control sample without
304 coagulant (wastewater). As the concentration of tannin increased, there was a progressive
305 reduction in TMP rise, indicating a greater filtration efficiency and a lower membrane fouling
306 tendency. The control sample, without coagulant, shows a sharp increase in TMP, requiring
307 three water recirculation cleanings to achieve an 80% permeate recovery rate, highlighting the
308 challenges of filtration without pre-treatment. Notably, for concentrations over 30 mg L^{-1} of
309 tannin (TAN-30), TMP remains almost constant, even at high permeate recovery rates (80%).
310 There is no significant difference between the TAN-30 and TAN-50 concentrations, suggesting

311 that from 30 mg L⁻¹ of coagulant onwards, the membrane fouling mitigation is close to its
312 maximum efficiency, with no further relevant benefits from increasing the tannin
313 concentration.

314 Figure 3-b illustrates the resistances associated with fouling, derived from the TMP
315 variation data of the filterability tests. The total fouling resistance is divided into internal
316 fouling, which corresponds to the resistance related to material deposition inside and adsorbed
317 onto the membrane, and external fouling, which represents the resistance associated with the
318 formation of the cake layer on the membrane surface. Using 10 mg L⁻¹ of coagulant, the
319 reduction in fouling is minimal, with only a 3% decrease in total resistance compared to the
320 control (raw wastewater). At 20 mg L⁻¹, a more pronounced reduction is noted, with the total
321 resistance decreasing by approximately 54%. However, it is at 30 mg L⁻¹ when a drastic
322 reduction in fouling occurs, with an 94% drop in total resistance compared to the control. A
323 further reduction in total resistance is still observed with the addition of 50 mg L⁻¹ (97%), but
324 much less pronounced. The total fouling resistance in the tests with 80% permeate recovery
325 reduced from 39.1x10¹¹ m⁻¹ (raw wastewater) to 2.1x10¹¹ m⁻¹ and 1.1·10¹¹ m⁻¹ with 30 and 50
326 mg L⁻¹ of tannin coagulant, respectively.

327 Regarding the location of the deposit, i.e., external and internal, the tannin-based
328 coagulant showed a more pronounced impact on external resistance (cake layer), which was
329 significantly reduced as the coagulant concentration increases, especially after 30 mg L⁻¹
330 (Figure 3b). This significant reduction in external resistance suggests that the coagulant
331 predominantly mitigates the formation of external fouling, while internal resistance also
332 decreases, but to a lesser extent. Despite the contribution of internal fouling becoming more
333 significant at higher coagulant concentrations, representing 45% and 53% of the total fouling
334 for concentrations of 30 and 50 mg L⁻¹ of tannin (Figure 3b), tannin shows a clear efficiency

335 in reducing both forms of resistance. At the end of the trials, internal resistance was reduced
 336 by 35% and 68% with the use of 30 and 50 mg L⁻¹ of tannin, respectively.

337
 338 **Figure 3.** TMP variation during the up-concentration process under constant flux operation (a)
 339 and fouling resistance (b).

340 The particle size distribution plays an important role in mitigating external fouling in
 341 ultrafiltration membranes. Figure 4 shows the impact of the tannin-based coagulant on the
 342 aggregation of particles in wastewater. In raw wastewater, the particle size distribution is
 343 dominated by small particles, with d(0.1) and d(0.5) values of 12 μm and 25 μm, respectively,
 344 indicating a high concentration of fine particles. Upon adding 10 mg L⁻¹ of tannin (TAN-10),
 345 a substantial increase in particle size was observed, with d(0.5) rising to 61.2 μm, suggesting
 346 effective flocculation. The trend continues with increasing tannin concentration, reaching a
 347 modal diameter of 60 μm with 50 mg L⁻¹, much higher than the value of 17 μm observed for
 348 the wastewater sample (Figure 4). Furthermore, for the tannin concentration of 50 mg L⁻¹,
 349 almost no particles smaller than 25 μm are observed, with d(0.1) and d(0.5) values of 28 and
 350 53 μm, respectively.

351 Larger flocs play an important role in improving particle removal efficiency through
 352 crossflow filtration, as they are less prone to deposit on membrane surfaces and form fouling
 353 layers. In MF and UF membrane systems, floc size directly influences the back-transport of

354 particles from the membrane surface to the bulk solution. Smaller flocs generally exhibit lower
 355 back-transport velocities, making their removal less efficient and increasing the potential of
 356 fouling by forming a dense cake layer on the membrane surface [52]. However, in crossflow
 357 membrane filtration systems, shear forces can break down flocs into smaller particles, further
 358 intensifying fouling. Therefore, the results on external fouling reduction suggest that, in
 359 addition to significantly increasing floc size, the tannin-based coagulant likely promotes the
 360 formation of more resistant aggregates capable of maintaining their structure during tangential
 361 filtration. Indeed, the adsorption and bridge formation mechanisms of polymer coagulants,
 362 such as tannin, lead to the development of more stable flocs, which are more resistant to
 363 breakage under shear forces [26,53]. This hypothesis was supported by Texeira et al. [54], who
 364 demonstrated that tannin produced stronger flocs than aluminum sulfate, with a greater capacity
 365 to resist breakage under sudden variations in shear rate.

366

367 **Figure 4:** Particle size distribution in jar test experiments with tannin coagulant.

368 To validate the results obtained from the short-term filtration assays, long-term
 369 continuous filtration tests were conducted. For these assays, a new sample of wastewater was
 370 used, and its filtration was compared to the same wastewater coagulated and flocculated with
 371 30 mg L⁻¹ of tannin, selected based on the optimal results previously observed. Figure 5-a

372 shows the variation of TMP under constant flux (≈ 20 LMH), while Figure 5-b presents the
373 fouling resistance values measured during the experiments. The TMP profile in the raw
374 wastewater sample shows a continuous increase over time, indicating a progressive fouling of
375 the membrane. In contrast, the sample treated with 30 mg L^{-1} of tannin exhibits a significantly
376 slower increase in TMP. The raw wastewater exhibited a sharp rise in TMP after the first few
377 hours, while the coagulated and flocculated sample maintains a relatively stable TMP up to 6
378 h of continuous crossflow filtration, with only a gradual increase observed thereafter. By the
379 end of the experiment, the estimated fouling rate based in the data of Figure 5-a for the
380 wastewater treated with tannin was just $0.8 \text{ mbar}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, whereas the untreated wastewater
381 exhibited a significantly higher fouling rate of $2.5 \text{ mbar}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, which is three times greater.

382 The total fouling resistance for the raw wastewater sample was considerably higher than
383 that of the coagulated/flocculated sample, with a clear reduction in both internal and external
384 resistances when used 30 mg L^{-1} tannin (Figure 5-b). For the raw wastewater, the total fouling
385 resistance (R_f) reached $9.24 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$, with an external fouling resistance (R_{ext}) of
386 $7.75 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$ and an internal fouling resistance (R_{int}) of $1.50 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$. In contrast the total
387 resistance for the tannin-coagulated and flocculated wastewater with 30 mg L^{-1} dropped to
388 $2.76 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$, representing a reduction of approximately 70% compared to the raw wastewater.
389 The external resistance decreased to $2.28 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$, corresponding to a reduction of around 71%
390 compared to the control sample, while the internal resistance dropped to $4.79 \times 10^{10} \text{ m}^{-1}$. This
391 finding is consistent with the short-term tests, confirming the ability of tannin to significantly
392 decrease fouling, particularly the external fouling associated with the formation of the cake
393 layer on the membrane surface.

394

395 **Figure 5:** Average TMP and fouling resistance under constant flux filtration in a long-term
 396 trial with raw and coagulated/flocculated wastewater.

397 **3.1.1. Threshold flux**

398 The threshold flux tests on concentrated wastewater samples (80% permeate recovery)
 399 show a clear relationship between increasing concentrations of tannin-based coagulant and the
 400 improvement in this critical parameter (Figure 6). For the raw wastewater, the threshold flux
 401 was estimated at 16 LMH, representing the maximum operational flux before significant
 402 fouling occurs. Using 10 mg L⁻¹ tannin, the flux increased to 18 LMH, a 13% improvement
 403 over the control, indicating partial fouling mitigation. At 20 mg L⁻¹, the flux reached 21 LMH,
 404 a 31% improvement, which means a more effective reduction in fouling, particularly the
 405 external layer (cake formation). With a concentration of 30 mg L⁻¹, the flux rose to 22.5 LMH,
 406 a 41% increase. Finally, at 50 mg L⁻¹, it further increased to 24.5 LMH, an improvement of
 407 53%.

408 This rise in threshold flux indicates a better balance between permeate production and
 409 sustainable membrane operation, as the system can function at higher fluxes without reaching
 410 critical fouling thresholds. In submerged ultrafiltration membranes, typical operational fluxes
 411 range between 15 and 25 LMH [52,55,56], and these results demonstrate that tannin-based
 412 coagulants can raise the limiting flux to 24.5 LMH, pushing the system closer to the optimal

413 operational capacity. However, the smaller increase from 30 mg L⁻¹ to 50 mg L⁻¹ (only 8.9%)
 414 suggests that the coagulant's fouling reduction capacity approaches its limits beyond 30 mg
 415 L⁻¹.

416

417 **Figure 6:** Threshold flux estimated for wastewater samples.

418

418 3.2. Membrane foulants characterization and fouling mechanisms

419 The results in Figure 7 show a clear reduction in total foulants on the membrane surface
 420 (measured as concentrations of COD, TSS, proteins and carbohydrates) when different
 421 concentrations of tannin-based coagulant were used. The highest foulant level was recorded
 422 for the raw wastewater, with a COD of 10.9 mg m⁻², TSS of 8.74 mg m⁻², protein of 3.16 mg
 423 m⁻², and carbohydrate of 1.91 mg m⁻². The addition of 10 mg L⁻¹ tannin already resulted in
 424 reductions of these parameters, with COD dropping to 7.4 mg m⁻² (32% reduction) and TSS to
 425 4.05 mg m⁻² (53% reduction). As the concentration of the tannin coagulant increased, further
 426 reductions in foulants were observed, with the most significant changes occurring between 20
 427 and 30 mg L⁻¹. For instance, at 30 mg L⁻¹ of tannin, COD levels fell to 4.3 mg m⁻², while TSS
 428 dropped further to 2.7 mg m⁻². These reductions indicate that the coagulant was effective in

429 agglomerating particles and reducing the deposition of organic matter and solids on the
430 membrane, thereby decreasing external fouling.

431 The removal of proteins was particularly notable, decreasing by approximately 80%
432 compared to raw wastewater, from 3.16 g m⁻² to 0.62 g m⁻² (Figure 7-b). In contrast,
433 carbohydrate removal was less pronounced, with only a 39% reduction at 30 mg L⁻¹ of tannin,
434 going from 1.91 g m⁻² to 1.18 g m⁻². This difference between protein and carbohydrate removal
435 could be attributed to the cationic nature of tannin, which likely binds more efficiently to
436 negatively charged proteins, facilitating their aggregation and removal [57,58]. Carbohydrates,
437 being less negatively charged and more soluble in general, may be less affected by the
438 coagulation process, leading to a smaller reduction.

439 The decrease in foulants correlates well with the observed reduction in filtration
440 resistances during the membrane filtration tests. As the foulants on the membrane surface
441 decreased, particularly proteins and TSS, which contribute heavily to fouling layer formation,
442 the total resistance across the membrane also dropped significantly. The higher reduction of
443 proteins compared to carbohydrates is particularly important, as proteins tend to form dense,
444 gel-like layers that contribute more to fouling resistance [59–61]. These results are consistent
445 with Subtil et al. [9], which observed that protein fouling plays a more significant role than
446 carbohydrate fouling in DMF of wastewater. The study highlighted those targeted
447 modifications by incorporation of graphene oxide (GO) into membranes, significantly reduced
448 protein fouling and improved membrane performance, emphasizing the greater impact of
449 proteins on the fouling process. Therefore, by reducing protein deposition on the membrane,
450 the tannin coagulant effectively minimized the formation of a high resistance fouling layer,
451 resulting in lower increase of transmembrane pressure and improving membrane permeability.

452

453

454 **Figure 7:** Characterization of external foulants in terms of COD and TSS (a), and total
 455 biopolymers (b).

456 The analysis of foulants deposited on the membrane surface, combined with the LC-
 457 DOC data for dissolved compounds in the external fouling layer, provides comprehensive
 458 insight into the effectiveness of tannin-based coagulants in reducing membrane fouling. In this
 459 way, the LC-DOC data further highlights the reduction of specific dissolved organic fractions
 460 (Figure 8). For instance, biopolymers, which are key contributors to fouling due to their gel-
 461 like structure [42], were reduced from 22 g m^{-2} in the fouling layer raw wastewater (R-WW)
 462 to just 8.2 g m^{-2} in the filtration of wastewater with 30 mg L^{-1} of tannin (Figure 8-b). The same
 463 trend was observed in the supernatant of wastewater coagulated with tannin, where a reduction
 464 of approximately 82% in biopolymers was achieved with 30 mg L^{-1} (Figure 8-a). The removal
 465 of biopolymers is crucial, as they tend to form dense fouling layers that significantly increase
 466 resistance to filtration [62,63].

467 Although to a lesser extent than biopolymers, the LC-DOC results also showed a further
 468 reduction in humic substances, building blocks and LMW neutral compounds in the external
 469 fouling layer by the addition of tannin. Humic substances were reduced by approximately 21%,
 470 while building blocks, smaller organic compounds that contribute to the formation of larger
 471 organic macromolecules, were also reduced, with a 20% decrease. The reduction of LMW

472 neutral compounds deposition, which are more soluble and can adsorbed into membrane pores
473 [42], was also significant, with a 39% reduction compared to R-WW. Therefore, while
474 biopolymers accounted for 40% of the dissolved organic compounds in the external fouling
475 layer of R-WW, LMW neutrals became the predominant foulants at 30 mg L⁻¹ of tannin,
476 representing 36% of the dissolved compounds quantified by LC-DOC.

477 The internal fouling composition data from the LC-DOC analysis further clarifies the
478 impact of tannin-based coagulants on membrane fouling, particularly in terms of the deposition
479 of DOC matter adsorbed on the membrane surface or within its pores. In raw wastewater, in
480 contrast to what was observed in the composition of the external fouling layer, where
481 biopolymers were predominant, internal fouling is primarily driven by humic substances (11.2
482 g m⁻²) and LMW neutral compounds (8.5 g m⁻²), which account for 37% and 28% of the internal
483 fouling concentration, respectively. These compounds, mainly humic substances, are known to
484 form complex structures that contribute to fouling by means of adsorption and pore blockage,
485 ultimately resulting in the development of irreversible fouling [64,65]. The presence of
486 biopolymers, although in smaller amounts (5.6 g m⁻²), was also observed and could contribute
487 to internal fouling by forming gel-like layers, further increasing hydraulic resistance and
488 limiting membrane permeability.

489 The introduction of tannin-based coagulant significantly reduces internal foulants, as
490 evidenced by the sharp decline in biopolymer concentration (1.3 g m⁻²) and the substantial
491 reduction in humic substances (3.2 g m⁻²). At this tannin concentration, LMW neutral
492 compounds become the largest fraction of material desorbed from the membrane (4.0 g m⁻²),
493 accounting for 38% of all internal foulants. Although a 62% reduction in the amount of humic
494 substances was observed at 30 mg L⁻¹ on tannin compared to raw wastewater filtration, these
495 compounds still represent the second largest fraction of internal fouling (30%), demonstrating
496 their high adsorption capacity and pore-blocking potential in UF membranes.

497
 498 **Figure 8:** Concentration of dissolved organic carbon determined by LC-DOC in a) wastewater
 499 (raw and coagulated/flocculated) and in the tannin solution; and b) external foulants removed
 500 with DI water and internal foulants desorbed by chemical cleaning.

501
 502 In the supernatant of tannin-coagulated and flocculated wastewater (Figure 8-a R-WW
 503 and TAN-30), the reduction of humic substances was less significant than that of biopolymers
 504 (22% compared to 82%), while the lower molecular weight fractions (i.e., building blocks and
 505 LMW-neutrals) were not significantly affected (Figure 8-a). Despite this, as discussed
 506 previously, a marked reduction in the deposition within the membrane pores and on the surface
 507 (i.e., internal foulants) was observed during the filtration of this sample (Figure 8-b). This
 508 behavior may be related to changes in the characteristics of dissolved organic substances after
 509 coagulation with tannin, such as modifications in surface charges and hydrophobicity [66].
 510 These modifications could reduce the tendency of these substances, especially humic
 511 substance, to adsorb onto the membrane surface or into its pores [33,67]. Previous studies have
 512 shown that coagulation can alter the properties of dissolved compounds, limiting their
 513 interaction with the membrane surface and thus reducing fouling [67]. Furthermore, the
 514 formation of a cake layer on the membrane surface, even in small quantities, together with the
 515 electrostatic modifications promoted by the coagulant, could act as an additional barrier,
 516 mitigating the deposition of these compounds on the membrane and facilitating their removal
 517 during cleaning with DI water. The higher concentration of these compounds in the external

518 layer compared to the internal fouling (Figure 8-b) supports the hypothesis that the cake layer
519 created by the use of tannin-based coagulant still plays a crucial role in preventing irreversible
520 fouling, even with the significant reduction in external resistance. This suggests that tannin-
521 based coagulation not only mitigates external fouling but also plays a crucial role in reducing
522 internal fouling, leading to improved long-term membrane performance.

523 **3.2.1. Effect of tannin coagulant in the internal fouling**

524 In order to evaluate the impact of tannin as a foulant and its contribution in the internal
525 fouling resistance, static adsorption and hydraulic resistance tests were conducted, along with
526 an analysis of the dissolved carbon composition of the tannin solution using LC-DOC. The
527 results show that the equilibrium adsorption of tannin on the membrane surface reaches $33.7 \pm$
528 2.6 mg C m^{-2} , indicating that tannin can interact strongly with the membrane material. The LC-
529 DOC analysis (Figure 8-a) reveals that the tannin solution is primarily composed of LMW
530 neutrals (2.5 mg L^{-1}), which constitute 86% of the dissolved organic matter in the solution.
531 Since these LMW neutrals are too small to be retained by the UF membrane, their potential
532 contribution to fouling would primarily arise from adsorption onto the membrane surface rather
533 than physical blockage of the pores. This adsorption of LMW neutrals could lead to internal
534 fouling if a significant concentration of tannin remains in solution after coagulation.

535 However, the coagulation and flocculation process would largely prevent this by
536 incorporating most of the tannin into the aggregates formed, which would reduce the
537 concentration of free tannin left to interact with the membrane. In the case of tannin-coagulated
538 and flocculated wastewater at 50 mg L^{-1} (TAN-50), the internal resistance (Figure 9) was 0.54
539 $\times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$, which is significantly lower than that of raw wastewater ($1.71 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$) and even
540 lower than the resistance found for the filtration of DI water solution with 50 mg L^{-1} of tannin
541 ($0.70 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-1}$). This suggests that most of the tannin is indeed consumed in the aggregation
542 process, leading to a reduction in the dissolved organic matter from the coagulant that can cause

543 internal fouling. Thus, while the adsorption of LMW neutrals from tannin coagulant could
544 theoretically contribute to internal fouling, the tannin's primary role in fouling mitigation lies
545 in its ability to form large, easily removable aggregates, reducing both internal and external
546 fouling. The remaining dissolved fraction of organic compounds in the wastewater, especially
547 humic substances, present in greater concentration will be, therefore, responsible for the largest
548 portion of the resistance associated with internal fouling.

549 On the other hand, given the strong interaction between the coagulant and the
550 membrane, an overdose of the coagulant can lead to an increased concentration of low LMW
551 neutrals, which can adsorb on the membrane surface and pores. This can result in an increase
552 in internal resistance, contributing to hydraulically irreversible fouling. This interaction
553 highlights the importance of optimizing coagulant dosage to balance effective fouling
554 mitigation while avoiding excessive adsorption of LMW neutrals, which can exacerbate
555 internal fouling and lead to irreversible hydraulic resistance.

556 **Figure 9:** Comparison of internal fouling resistance of raw wastewater (R-WW), tannin-
557 coagulated and flocculated wastewater (C/F WW) and tannin solution (deionized water + 50
558 mg L⁻¹ of tannin).

560 3.2.2. Fouling mechanism

561 Given the obtained results, a fouling mechanism is proposed to describe the interactions
562 between the wastewater components and the membrane during the filtration process (Figure
563 10). In DMF of raw wastewater, the fouling mechanism is dominated by the deposition of fine
564 suspended solids, biopolymers and DOC, particularly humic substances and LMW compounds.
565 Total biopolymers, which include proteins and carbohydrates, form dense, gel-like layers on
566 the membrane surface, significantly increasing TMP and reducing membrane permeability.
567 Proteins, which are more abundant than carbohydrates, contribute heavily to this external
568 fouling by creating a compact and resistant cake layer. The higher concentration of fine solids
569 and proteins further enhanced external fouling, making it more difficult to remove and leading
570 to a sharp rise in TMP. In addition to the external cake layer formation, humic substances and
571 LMW neutrals compounds are adsorbed onto the membrane surface and in the pores, causing
572 internal fouling and increasing hydraulic resistance. This combination of a biopolymer-rich
573 cake layer and internal fouling results in severe fouling, necessitating frequent cleaning to
574 maintain membrane performance.

575 In contrast, when wastewater is treated with 30 mg L⁻¹ of tannin-based coagulant, the
576 fouling mechanism shifts significantly. The addition of tannin induces effective flocculation,
577 leading to the aggregation of smaller particles into larger, more stable flocs that are less prone
578 to depositing on the membrane surface. The total reduction in external fouling, particularly in
579 the total biopolymer cake layer, is primarily associated with a reduction in protein deposition.
580 Tannin efficiently promotes the formation of larger protein-based flocs, which reduces the
581 density and resistance of the external cake layer. As a result, TMP rises more slowly, and the
582 overall fouling resistance is greatly reduced. Though internal fouling still occurs due to humic
583 substances and LMW neutrals, it is less severe than in raw wastewater. The tannin coagulant
584 appears to modify the surface interactions between the dissolved organic matter (DOM) and
585 the membrane, which, combined with physical filtration of the cake layer, leads to reduced

586 adsorption and mitigation of internal fouling. This combined effect on both external and
 587 internal fouling significantly improves long-term membrane performance and reduces the need
 588 for frequent cleaning.

589
 590 **Figure 10:** Schematic representation of foulant deposition in raw wastewater and wastewater
 591 coagulated with 30 mg L⁻¹ of tannin.

592 3.3. COD removal and methane production

593 The COD removal results for the different filtration tests are shown in Figure 11-a. In
 594 addition to the complete removal of particulate COD, as expected, a reduction in the soluble
 595 COD fraction was also observed due to the use of the UF membrane. The soluble COD
 596 concentration in the wastewater, initially $122 \pm 5 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ L}^{-1}$, was reduced to $85 \pm 4 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ L}^{-1}$
 597 in the permeate from raw wastewater filtered without the use of a coagulant. A slight
 598 improvement compared to raw wastewater was achieved with the use of tannin at
 599 concentrations ranging from 10 to 30 mg L⁻¹. At these tannin concentrations, COD removal in
 600 the permeate varied between 68% and 71%, whereas removal in the raw wastewater was 65%.
 601 This trend aligns with studies demonstrating the effectiveness of natural coagulants, such as
 602 tannin, in promoting the aggregation of higher molecular weight organic compounds, which
 603 facilitates their separation during membrane filtration [35,68]. However, at a dosage of 50 mg
 604 L⁻¹, the removal efficiency dropped to 51%, suggesting that an excess of tannin may generate

605 a dissolved fraction of LMW organic compounds, predominantly neutral (Figure 8-a), which
 606 are not fully retained by the membrane, thereby contributing to the COD in the permeate.

607
 608 **Figure 11:** Concentration of COD in raw wastewater (R-WW), in the permeate of UF and
 609 removal efficiency and; b) BMP of the DMF concentrates and activated sludge from WWTP-
 610 UAM.

611 The COD behavior in the concentrate shows an increasing trend as the tannin dosage
 612 increases, with COD concentrations in the concentrate ranging from 844 mg L⁻¹ in R-WW to
 613 up to 1270 mg L⁻¹ in the sample with 50 mg L⁻¹ of coagulant. This increase can be attributed
 614 to the retention of higher molecular weight organic compounds and the contribution of the
 615 coagulant itself, which has an organic load of 670 mg COD g⁻¹ tannin. At higher dosages, the
 616 accumulation of organic matter in the concentrate may be beneficial for its subsequent
 617 management, such as anaerobic digestion, as a higher organic content is advantageous for
 618 potential biogas production, improving energy recovery. It is worth noting that significantly
 619 high COD concentrations in the concentrate, ranging from 8,000 to 20,000 mg L⁻¹, are obtained
 620 with higher permeate recovery rates (95-98%), usually applied in DMF systems [69].

621 The BMP test results assessing the effect of tannin use are shown in Figure 11-b. It can be
 622 observed that the addition of tannin (TAN-50) to improve filtration did not reduce methane

623 production. After 30 days of testing, values of 377 ± 11 mL CH₄ STP g⁻¹ VS and 391 ± 35 mL
624 CH₄ STP g⁻¹ VS were obtained for the concentrated raw wastewater and with 50 mg L⁻¹ of
625 tannin, respectively. Although the difference in methane production yield was relatively small
626 between the DMF concentrate samples, the initial methane production rate with tannin was
627 higher. In the first 15 d, the tannin-containing concentrate had already reached around 332 mL
628 CH₄ STP g⁻¹ VS, while the sample with only raw wastewater showed lower values (267 mL
629 CH₄ STP g⁻¹ VS). This accelerated methane production suggests that tannin, besides acting as
630 a coagulant, also serves as an additional source of easily biodegradable organic matter, which
631 could enhance methane production in the early stages of the process.

632 In Table 2, BMP values from the literature for DMF concentrates, both with and without
633 coagulants, are presented. Although making a direct comparison between the BMP values in
634 this study and those reported by other authors is challenging, due to variations in wastewater
635 composition and treatment processes, the values observed here fall within the range
636 documented in the literature. For wastewater coagulated with polyaluminum chloride (PACl),
637 BMP values ranged from 281 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ VS [27] to 407 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ VS [24], depending on
638 concentration and experimental conditions. The BMP for tannin-coagulated wastewater was
639 391 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ VS (this study), indicating a high potential for biogas production. Moreover,
640 when comparing the BMP value of sludge from conventional activated sludge systems (Figure
641 11-b), it is evident that the DMF concentrate offers greater potential for energy recovery.
642 Similar values (377 – 391 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ VS) are typically achieved by high-load activated sludge
643 systems under an SRT of less than 2 days.

644

645

646

647

648 **Table 2:** Methane yield for raw wastewater and coagulated wastewater from the DMF system.

DMF concentrate	Coagulant	Dose (mg L ⁻¹)	BMP (mL CH ₄ g ⁻¹ VS _{add})	Reference
Raw wastewater	-	-	323	[70]
		-	377	This study
		30	281	[27]
Coagulated wastewater	PACl	30	367	[71]
		4.3 mg-Al/L)	407	[24]
	Tannin	50	391	This study

649

650 4. Conclusions

651 This study investigated the effect of tannin-based coagulants on organic matter
652 concentration in DMF systems and their impact on methane production during anaerobic
653 digestion. Tannin addition significantly improved membrane filtration performance by
654 reducing total fouling resistance, particularly in the external fouling layer associated with cake
655 formation. At a concentration of 30 mg L⁻¹ or higher, tannin effectively mitigated fouling,
656 largely by promoting particle aggregation and reducing biopolymer deposition on the
657 membrane. This reduction in biopolymers, especially proteins, led to a substantial decrease in
658 external fouling resistance, while internal fouling was also minimized, though to a lesser extent.
659 Additionally, the use of tannin-based coagulants did not hinder methane production in
660 anaerobic digestion tests. In fact, tannin acted as an additional source of easily biodegradable
661 organic matter, accelerating the methane production rate in the early stages. The methane yields
662 of tannin-coagulated wastewater (391 mL CH₄ STP g⁻¹ VS) were comparable to or higher than
663 those reported in the literature for coagulated wastewater. Tannin-based coagulants offer a
664 promising alternative as coagulants in DMF systems, providing dual benefits of enhanced
665 filtration performance and energy recovery through biogas production. Further research could

666 explore the long-term stability of tannin-coagulated systems and their application in full-scale
667 operations.

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671 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process**

672
673 During the preparation of this work the authors used site GPT in order to improve language
674 and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as
675 needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

677

678 **CRedit author statement**

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685 **References**

- 686 [1] J. Wan, J. Gu, Q. Zhao, Y. Liu, COD capture: a feasible option towards energy self-
687 sufficient domestic wastewater treatment, Nat. Publ. Gr. (2016).
688 <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep25054>.
- 689 [2] T. Sugiyama, Y. Ito, A. Hafuka, K. Kimura, Efficient direct membrane filtration (DMF)
690 of municipal wastewater for carbon recovery: Application of a simple pretreatment and
691 selection of an appropriate membrane pore size, Water Res. 221 (2022) 118810.
692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.118810>.

- 693 [3] T.A. Nascimento, M.P. Miranda, Continuous municipal wastewater up-concentration by
694 direct membrane filtration, considering the effect of intermittent gas scouring and
695 threshold flux determination, *J. Water Process Eng.* 39 (2021) 101733.
696 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2020.101733>.
- 697 [4] K. Kimura, D. Honoki, T. Sato, Effective physical cleaning and adequate membrane
698 flux for direct membrane filtration (DMF) of municipal wastewater: Up-concentration
699 of organic matter for efficient energy recovery, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 181 (2017) 37–43.
700 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2017.03.005>.
- 701 [5] E. Ferrera, I. Ruigómez, L. Vera, Pilot scale application of a rotating hollow fibre
702 membrane for direct membrane filtration of domestic wastewater, *J. Water Process Eng.*
703 58 (2024) 104755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JWPE.2023.104755>.
- 704 [6] P. Sanchis-Perucho, D. Aguado, J. Ferrer, A. Seco, Á. Robles, A comprehensive review
705 of the direct membrane filtration of municipal wastewater, *Environ. Technol. Innov.* 35
706 (2024) 103732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ETI.2024.103732>.
- 707 [7] H. Guven, R.K. Dereli, H. Ozgun, M.E. Ersahin, I. Ozturk, Towards sustainable and
708 energy efficient municipal wastewater treatment by up-concentration of organics, *Prog.*
709 *Energy Combust. Sci.* 70 (2019) 145–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2018.10.002>.
- 710 [8] T.A. Nascimento, M.P. Miranda, Control strategies for the long-term operation of direct
711 membrane filtration of municipal wastewater, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2021) 105335.
712 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105335>.
- 713 [9] E.L. Subtil, R. Almeria Raggio, H.G. Lemos, G. Scaratti, J. García, P. Le-Clech, Direct
714 membrane filtration (DMF) of municipal wastewater by mixed matrix membranes
715 (MMMs) filled with graphene oxide (GO): Towards a circular sanitation model, *Chem.*
716 *Eng. J.* 441 (2022) 136004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2022.136004>.
- 717 [10] S. Hube, J. Wang, L.N. Sim, D. Dagmar' Dagmar'olafsdóttir, H. Chong, B. Wu, Fouling

- 718 and mitigation mechanisms during direct microfiltration and ultrafiltration of primary
719 wastewater, *J. Water Process Eng.* 44 (2021) 2214–7144.
720 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2021.102331>.
- 721 [11] Y.-X. Zhao, P. Li, R.-H. Li, X.-Y. Li, Characterization and mitigation of the fouling of
722 flat-sheet ceramic membranes for direct filtration of the coagulated domestic
723 wastewater, *J. Hazard. Mater. J.* 385 (2019) 121557.
724 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.121557>.
- 725 [12] B.C. Huang, Y.F. Guan, W. Chen, H.Q. Yu, Membrane fouling characteristics and
726 mitigation in a coagulation-assisted microfiltration process for municipal wastewater
727 pretreatment, *Water Res.* 123 (2017) 216–223.
728 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.06.080>.
- 729 [13] K. Kimura, M. Yamakawa, A. Hafuka, Direct membrane filtration (DMF) for recovery
730 of organic matter in municipal wastewater using small amounts of chemicals and energy,
731 *Chemosphere.* 277 (2021) 130244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130244>.
- 732 [14] Z. Jin, F. Meng, H. Gong, X. Hu, K. Wang, Optimized scaling-up towards commercial
733 ultrafiltration-pre-concentration-based integrated sewage resource recovery for cleaner
734 production, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122275>.
- 735 [15] H. Gong, Z. Jin, H. Xu, Q. Yuan, J. Zuo, J. Wu, K. Wang, Enhanced membrane-based
736 pre-concentration improves wastewater organic matter recovery: Pilot-scale
737 performance and membrane fouling, *J. Clean. Prod.* 206 (2019) 307–314.
738 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.209>.
- 739 [16] Y. xia Zhao, P. Li, R. hong Li, X. yan Li, Direct filtration for the treatment of the
740 coagulated domestic sewage using flat-sheet ceramic membranes, *Chemosphere.* 223
741 (2019) 383–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.02.055>.
- 742 [17] C. He, K. Wang, W. Wang, K. Fang, Revealing the fouling characteristics in membrane-

- 743 based primary treatment (MPT) of municipal wastewater and the antifouling mechanism
744 of influent conditioning, *J. Water Process Eng.* 54 (2023) 103920.
745 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2023.103920>.
- 746 [18] W. Lun Ang, A. Wahab Mohammad, State of the art and sustainability of natural
747 coagulants in water and wastewater treatment, (2020).
748 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121267>.
- 749 [19] J. Gonçalves, A.A. Baldovi, B. Chyoshi, L. Zanata, A.M. Salcedo, E.L. Subtil, L.H.G.
750 Coelho, effect of aluminum sulfate and cationic polymer addition in the mixed liquor of
751 a submerged membrane bioreactor (smbr): sludge characteristics and orthophosphate
752 removal in batch experiments, *Brazilian J. Chem. Eng.* 36 (n.d.) 693–703.
753 <https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-6632.20190362s20180128>.
- 754 [20] R.A. Ragio, L.F. Miyazaki, M.A. De Oliveira, L.H.G. Coelho, R.D.F. Bueno, E.L.
755 Subtil, Pre-coagulation assisted ultrafiltration membrane process for anaerobic effluent,
756 *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 8 (2020) 104066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104066>.
- 757 [21] Y. Chen, Y. Wu, D. Wang, H. Li, Q. Wang, Y. Liu, L. Peng, Q. Yang, X. Li, G. Zeng,
758 Y. Chen, Understanding the mechanisms of how poly aluminium chloride inhibits short-
759 chain fatty acids production from anaerobic fermentation of waste activated sludge,
760 *Chem. Eng. J.* 334 (2018) 1351–1360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2017.11.064>.
- 761 [22] L. Lin, R. hong Li, Z. yuan Yang, X. yan Li, Effect of coagulant on acidogenic
762 fermentation of sludge from enhanced primary sedimentation for resource recovery:
763 Comparison between FeCl_3 and PACl , *Chem. Eng. J.* 325 (2017) 681–689.
764 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2017.05.130>.
- 765 [23] V. Diamantis, W. Verstraete, A. Eftaxias, B. Bundervoet, S.E. Vlaeminck, P. Melidis,
766 A. Aivasidis, Sewage pre-concentration for maximum recovery and reuse at
767 decentralized level, *Water Sci. Technol.* 67 (2013) 1188–1193.

- 768 <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2013.639>.
- 769 [24] A. Hafuka, T. Takahashi, K. Kimura, Anaerobic digestibility of up-concentrated organic
770 matter obtained from direct membrane filtration of municipal wastewater, (2020).
771 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2020.107692>.
- 772 [25] E. Aghaei, Z. Wang, B. Tadesse, C.B. Tabelin, Z. Quadir, R.D. Alorro, Performance
773 Evaluation of Fe-Al Bimetallic Particles for the Removal of Potentially Toxic Elements
774 from Combined Acid Mine Drainage-Effluents from Refractory Gold Ore Processing,
775 *Miner.* 2021, Vol. 11, Page 590. 11 (2021) 590. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MIN11060590>.
- 776 [26] A. Ibrahim, A.Z. Yaser, J. Lamaming, Synthesising tannin-based coagulants for water
777 and wastewater application: A review, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2020) 105007.
778 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.105007>.
- 779 [27] Z. Jin, H. Gong, H. Temmink, H. Nie, J. Wu, J. Zuo, K. Wang, Efficient sewage pre-
780 concentration with combined coagulation microfiltration for organic matter recovery,
781 *Chem. Eng. J.* 292 (2016) 130–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.02.024>.
- 782 [28] A. Nath, A. Mishra, P. Prakash Pande, A review natural polymeric coagulants in
783 wastewater treatment, (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.551>.
- 784 [29] M. Saleem, R.T. Bachmann, A contemporary review on plant-based coagulants for
785 applications in water treatment, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 72 (2019) 281–297.
786 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JIEC.2018.12.029>.
- 787 [30] J. Sánchez-Martín, M. González-Velasco, J. Beltrán-Heredia, Surface water treatment
788 with tannin-based coagulants from Quebracho (*Schinopsis balansae*), *Chem. Eng. J.* 165
789 (2010) 851–858. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2010.10.030>.
- 790 [31] R.A. Ragio, C.C. Arantes, E.L. Subtil, R. Almeria, C.C. Arantes, E.L. Subtil, R.A.
791 Ragio, C.C. Arantes, E.L. Subtil, Performance assessment and economic aspects for
792 water reclamation from UASB reactor effluent: Influence of coagulant type and

- 793 membrane pore size reactor effluent : Influence of coagulant type and membrane pore
794 size, Sep. Sci. Technol. 00 (2024) 1–17.
795 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2024.2351096>.
- 796 [32] A.M. Ferrari-Lima, R.G. Marques, N.R.C. Fernandes-Machado, M.L. Gimenes,
797 Photodegradation of petrol station wastewater after coagulation/flocculation with
798 tannin-based coagulant, Catal. Today. 209 (2013) 79–83.
799 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CATTOD.2012.10.022>.
- 800 [33] R.A. Raggio, A.C. Santana, E.L. Subtil, Landfill Leachate and Coagulants Addition
801 Effects on Membrane Bioreactor Mixed Liquor: Filterability, Fouling, and Pollutant
802 Removal, Membranes (Basel). 14 (2024) 212.
803 <https://doi.org/10.3390/MEMBRANES14100212/S1>.
- 804 [34] R. Gutiérrez, F. Passos, I. Ferrer, E. Uggetti, J. García, Harvesting microalgae from
805 wastewater treatment systems with natural flocculants: Effect on biomass settling and
806 biogas production, Algal Res. 9 (2015) 204–211.
807 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2015.03.010>.
- 808 [35] R.A. Raggio, C.C. Arantes, J. Garcia, E.L. Subtil, Assessment of Natural Tannin-Based
809 Coagulant for Effective Ultrafiltration (Uf) of Uasb Effluent: Fouling Mechanisms,
810 Pollutant Removal and Water Reclamation Feasibility, J. Environ. Chem. Eng. 11
811 (2023) 109778. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4303090>.
- 812 [36] R. Franci, L. Zotele, E. Lucas, Investigating the use of coagulants and Ca²⁺-rich steel
813 residues as an anti-fouling strategy in the ultrafiltration of microalgae : Towards
814 sustainable resource recovery from wastewater, Sep. Purif. Technol. 349 (2024) 127738.
815 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2024.127738>.
- 816 [37] H. Guo, Y. Wyart, J. Perot, F. Nauleau, P. Moulin, Low-pressure membrane integrity
817 tests for drinking water treatment: A review, Water Res. 44 (2010) 41–57.

- 818 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2009.09.032>.
- 819 [38] L.H. Lamb, O.G. Decusati, MANUFACTURING PROCESS FOR QUATERNARY
820 AMMONIUM TANNATE, A VEGETABLE COAGULATING/FLOCCULATING
821 AGENT, US 6,478,986 B1, 2002.
- 822 [39] N. Graham, F. Gang, G. Fowler, M. Watts, Characterisation and coagulation
823 performance of a tannin-based cationic polymer: A preliminary assessment, *Colloids
824 Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 327 (2008) 9–16.
825 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COLSURFA.2008.05.045>.
- 826 [40] T.A. Malkoske, P.R. Bérubé, R.C. Andrews, Leveraging coagulation mechanisms to
827 reduce fouling and increase natural organic matter removal during
828 coagulation/flocculation-ultrafiltration treatment, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 327 (2023)
829 124877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SEPPUR.2023.124877>.
- 830 [41] M. Chai, Y. Ye, V. Chen, Separation and concentration of milk proteins with a
831 submerged membrane vibrational system, *J. Memb. Sci.* 524 (2017) 305–314.
832 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MEMSCI.2016.11.043>.
- 833 [42] N. Subhi, G. Leslie, V. Chen, P. Le-Clech, Organic Fouling of Ultrafiltration Membrane:
834 Detailed Characterization by Liquid Chromatography with Organic Carbon Detector
835 (LC-OCD), *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 48 (2012) 199–207.
836 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2012.686552>.
- 837 [43] N. Li, Y. Tian, J. Zhao, J. Zhang, L. Kong, J. Zhang, W. Zuo, Static adsorption of
838 protein-polysaccharide hybrids on hydrophilic modified membranes based on atomic
839 layer deposition: Anti-fouling performance and mechanism insight, *J. Memb. Sci.* 548
840 (2018) 470–480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MEMSCI.2017.11.063>.
- 841 [44] J.A. Villamil, A.F. Mohedano, J.J. Rodriguez, M.A. de la Rubia, Valorisation of the
842 liquid fraction from hydrothermal carbonisation of sewage sludge by anaerobic

- 843 digestion, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 93 (2018) 450–456.
844 <https://doi.org/10.1002/JCTB.5375>.
- 845 [45] I. Angelidaki, W. Sanders, Assessment of the anaerobic biodegradability of
846 macropollutants, *Rev. Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 3 (2004) 117–129.
847 <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11157-004-2502-3/METRICS>.
- 848 [46] M.A. De la Rubia, J.A. Villamil, J.J. Rodriguez, A.F. Mohedano, Effect of inoculum
849 source and initial concentration on the anaerobic digestion of the liquid fraction from
850 hydrothermal carbonisation of sewage sludge, *Renew. Energy.* 127 (2018) 697–704.
851 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RENENE.2018.05.002>.
- 852 [47] M.P. Diez, E. Barahona, M.A. de la Rubia, A.F. Mohedano, E. Diaz, Valorization of
853 process water from hydrothermal carbonization of food waste by dark fermentation, *Int.*
854 *J. Hydrogen Energy.* 89 (2024) 1383–1393.
855 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2024.09.289>.
- 856 [48] APHA, Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, 23rd ed.,
857 Water Environment Federation, American Public Health Association, American Water
858 Works Association, 2017.
- 859 [49] F. Raposo, M.A. de la Rubia, R. Borja, M. Alaiz, Assessment of a modified and
860 optimised method for determining chemical oxygen demand of solid substrates and
861 solutions with high suspended solid content, *Talanta.* 76 (2008) 448–453.
862 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TALANTA.2008.03.030>.
- 863 [50] O. Lowry, N. Rosebrough, A. Lewis, R. Randall, Protein measurement with the Folin
864 Phenol Reagent, *J. Biol. Chem.* 193 (1951) 265–275.
- 865 [51] A.A. Albalasmeh, A.A. Berhe, T.A. Ghezzehei, A new method for rapid determination
866 of carbohydrate and total carbon concentrations using UV spectrophotometry,
867 *Carbohydr. Polym.* 97 (2013) 253–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2013.04.072>.

- 868 [52] H.-D. Park, I.-S. Chang, K.-J. Lee, Principles of Membrane Bioreactors for Wastewater
869 Treatment, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b18368>.
- 870 [53] P. Jarvis, B. Jefferson, S.A. Parsons, Floc structural characteristics using conventional
871 coagulation for a high doc, low alkalinity surface water source, *Water Res.* 40 (2006)
872 2727–2737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WATRES.2006.04.024>.
- 873 [54] M.S. Teixeira, L.G. Speranza, I.C. da Silva, R.B. Moruzzi, G.H.R. Silva, Tannin-based
874 coagulant for harvesting microalgae cultivated in wastewater: Efficiency, floc
875 morphology and products characterization, *Sci. Total Environ.* 807 (2022) 150776.
876 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2021.150776>.
- 877 [55] E.L. Subtil, M.V. Silva, B.A. Lotto, M.R.D. Moretto, J.C. Mierzwa, Pilot-scale
878 investigation on the feasibility of simultaneous nitrification and denitrification (SND) in
879 a continuous flow single-stage membrane bioreactor, *J. Water Process Eng.* 32 (2019).
880 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2019.100995>.
- 881 [56] E.L. Subtil, I. Hespanhol, J.C. Mierzwa, Submerged membrane bioreactor (sMBR): A
882 promising alternative to wastewater treatment for water reuse, *Rev. Ambient. e Agua.* 8
883 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.4136/ambi-agua.1230>.
- 884 [57] O.N. Abiola, *Polymers for Coagulation and Flocculation in Water Treatment*, (2019)
885 77–92. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00743-0_4.
- 886 [58] E.K. Tetteh, S. Rathilal, E.K. Tetteh, S. Rathilal, Application of Organic Coagulants in
887 Water and Wastewater Treatment, *Org. Polym.* (2019).
888 <https://doi.org/10.5772/INTECHOPEN.84556>.
- 889 [59] D. Sioutopoulos, A. Karabelas, V. Mappas, Membrane Fouling Due to Protein—
890 Polysaccharide Mixtures in Dead-End Ultrafiltration; the Effect of Permeation Flux on
891 Fouling Resistance, *Membr.* 2019, Vol. 9, Page 21. 9 (2019) 21.
892 <https://doi.org/10.3390/MEMBRANES9020021>.

- 893 [60] H.G. Lemos, R.A. Ragio, A.C.S. Conceição, E.C. Venancio, J.C. Mierzwa, E.L. Subtil,
894 Assessment of mixed matrix membranes (MMMs) incorporated with graphene oxide
895 (GO) for co-treatment of wastewater and landfill leachate (LFL) in a membrane
896 bioreactor (MBR), *Chem. Eng. J.* 425 (2021).
897 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131772>.
- 898 [61] E.L. Subtil, J. Gonçalves, H.G. Lemos, E.C. Venancio, J.C. Mierzwa, J. dos Santos de
899 Souza, W. Alves, P. Le-Clech, Preparation and characterization of a new composite
900 conductive polyethersulfone membrane using polyaniline (PANI) and reduced graphene
901 oxide (rGO), *Chem. Eng. J.* 390 (2020) 124612.
902 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.124612>.
- 903 [62] H. Xu, K. Xiao, X. Wang, S. Liang, C. Wei, X. Wen, X. Huang, Outlining the Roles of
904 Membrane-Foulant and Foulant-Foulant Interactions in Organic Fouling During
905 Microfiltration and Ultrafiltration: A Mini-Review, *Front. Chem.* 8 (2020) 417.
906 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2020.00417>.
- 907 [63] R. Ragio, H. Lemos, G. Leocadio, J.C. Mierzwa, D. Biron, J.C.A. Espíndola, T.
908 Castilho, M. Escote, J.H.H. Rossato, E.L. Subtil, Performance comparison of modified
909 polyethersulfone membrane with graphene oxide and molybdenum disulfide for
910 effective filtration of urban surface water, *Sep. Purif. Technol. J.* 356 (2025) 130001.
911 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2024.130001>.
- 912 [64] W. Huang, Y. Zhu, L. Wang, W. Lv, B. Dong, W. Zhou, Reversible and irreversible
913 membrane fouling in hollow-fiber UF membranes filtering surface water: effects of
914 ozone/powdered activated carbon treatment, *RSC Adv.* 11 (2021) 10323–10335.
915 <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0RA09820E>.
- 916 [65] T. Fane, Irreversible Fouling, *Encycl. Membr.* (2015) 1–2. [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-40872-4_328-1)
917 [3-642-40872-4_328-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-40872-4_328-1).

- 918 [66] K. Grenda, J. Arnold, D. Hunkeler, J.A.F. Gamelas, M.G. Rasteiro, Tannin-based
919 coagulants from laboratory to pilot plant scales for coloured wastewater treatment,
920 *BioResources*. 13 (2018) 2727–2747.
- 921 [67] S.A. Aly, W.B. Anderson, P.M. Huck, In-line coagulation assessment for ultrafiltration
922 fouling reduction to treat secondary effluent for water reuse, *Water Sci. Technol.* 83
923 (2021) 284–296. <https://doi.org/10.2166/WST.2020.571>.
- 924 [68] A. Matilainen, M. Vepsäläinen, M. Sillanpää, Natural organic matter removal by
925 coagulation during drinking water treatment: A review, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 159
926 (2010) 189–197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CIS.2010.06.007>.
- 927 [69] C. He, K. Wang, K. Fang, H. Gong, Z. Jin, Q. He, Q. Wang, Up-concentration processes
928 of organics for municipal wastewater treatment: New trends in separation, *Sci. Total*
929 *Environ.* 787 (2021) 147690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147690>.
- 930 [70] T.A. Nascimento, F.R. Mejía, F. Fdz-Polanco, M. Peña Miranda, Improvement of
931 municipal wastewater pretreatment by direct membrane filtration, *Environ. Technol.* 38
932 (2017) 2562–2572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2016.1271017>.
- 933 [71] H. Gong, Z. Jin, H. Xu, Q. Yuan, J. Zuo, J. Wu, K. Wang, Enhanced membrane-based
934 pre-concentration improves wastewater organic matter recovery: Pilot-scale
935 performance and membrane fouling, *J. Clean. Prod.* 206 (2019) 307–314.
936 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.209>.
- 937
- 938
- 939
- 940
- 941
- 942